

Can hemogram parameters be an indicator for the systemic effects of inhaled corticosteroids in COPD patients? A comparative review of different corticosteroids and different inhaler techniques

Ramazan Öcal^{*1} and Nesrin Öcal[□]

^{*}Health Sciences University, Gulhane Medical Faculty, Department of Hematology, Ankara, Turkey., [□]Health Sciences University, Gulhane Medical Faculty, Department of Chest Diseases, Ankara, Turkey.

ABSTRACT

Background: While it is well known that systemic steroids may cause changes in hemogram parameters, it is essential whether the use of inhaled corticosteroid (ICS) leads to changes in hemogram parameters. In this study, we aimed to find out the effects of ICSs on hemogram in the comparison between different inhaler techniques of different corticosteroids.

Methods: The medical records of 100 ICS user COPD patients and 100 ICS non-user COPD patients were reviewed retrospectively. Demographic data, complete blood count values, GOLD groups, history of pneumonia in the last year, the content of bronchodilator treatments and valid inhaler techniques were recorded.

Results: Significant increase was detected in the mean MCHC, Eosinophil%, $\#$ Eosinophil values among ICS non-users; and the mean RDW-CV, MCV, WBC, Neutrophil% and $\#$ Neutrophil values among ICS users ($p < 0.05$). Anaemia was observed in 16(%) of ICS non-users and 31(%) of ICS users ($p = 0.05$). Fluticasone propionate group had the highest rate of pneumonia in the last year (11.1%) ($p = 0.05$). WBC, Neutrophil%, $\#$ Neutrophil were significantly lower in budesonide group ($p = 0.012$, $p = 0.05$, $p = 0.048$ respectively). The mean Monocyte% and $\#$ Monocyte were significantly lower in beclomethasone group ($p = 0.043$, $p = 0.05$, respectively). Nebulizer users had the highest frequency of pneumonia diagnosis in the last year (30%) ($p = 0.05$). The mean WBC was significantly higher in blister-based DPI users ($9.4 \pm 2.3 \times 10^3 \text{ cell}/\mu\text{L}$) ($p = 0.044$). The frequency of pneumonia was increased by 3 fold/year in ICS users. Among the ICS users, the mean WBC and $\#$ Neutrophil values of these 9 patients were significantly higher than those without pneumonia history ($10.8 \pm 2.5 \times 10^3 \text{ cell}/\mu\text{L}$ and $6.3 \pm 2.3 \times 10^3 \text{ cell}$; $p = 0.042$ and $p = 0.05$, respectively).

Conclusion: The results of the study indicate that changes in hemogram parameters may be associated with ICS use and that these changes may be helpful in predicting systemic side effects of ICSs.

KEYWORDS inhaled corticosteroid, side effect, hemogram, complete blood count, neutrophil

Copyright © 2020 by the Bulgarian Association of Young Surgeons
DOI:10.5455/IJMRCR.Alterations-hemogram-parameters-with-inhaled-corticosteroids

First Received: October 14, 2019

Accepted: November 04, 2019

Editor-in-chief: Ivan Inkov (BG)

¹Health Sciences University, Gulhane Medical Faculty, Department of Hematology, Ankara, Turkey.; Email: nesrinbaygin@yahoo.com

Introduction

Corticosteroids are of historical importance in the treatment of obstructive airway diseases. Inhaled corticosteroid (ICS) has been accepted as one of the cornerstones in the treatment of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease (COPD) patients to reduce the side effect profile of corticosteroids which have been used in systemic forms for many years. ICSs, marketed in combination forms, mostly with long-acting beta-agonists (LABA), have been widely used in all stages of COPD. However, subsequent studies have shown that inflammation in COPD is irreversible mainly and inflammation status varies among patients [1-3].

Additionally, low systemic absorption of ICSs has also been documented, with minor effects on the hypothalamic-pituitary-adrenal axis, dysregulation on carbohydrate and lipid metabolisms, bone loss, skin thinning, increased cataract formation, and behavioural abnormalities. Due to the anti-inflammatory and immunosuppressive effects of corticosteroids, pneumonia is also a potential side effect of ICSs [4,5]. Considering all these impact and side effects profile, the use of ICS has been restricted in recent years in line with the profit/loss ratio. On the other hand, it is an accepted fact that some COPD patients benefit more from ICSs. This raises the question of how and in whom ICSs have more side effects, and if we can predict and prevent such systemic effects. It has been well established that the cumulative dose influences risk of systemic side effects from ICS, individual differences in response to the glucocorticoid, delivery system, and degree to which the drug is absorbed in different sites (e.g. lung versus gastrointestinal tract). Studies on this subject are generally based on comparison with the control group after short-term ICS use [6]. However, it is not clear whether the measurable short-term effects of ICSs translate into a significant clinical consequence with long-term use.

The patient's inhaler technique, steroid dose and personal metabolic properties are seen as the most determinant factors on the possible systemic effects of ICSs. The most important mechanism in the systemic circulation is that the steroid taken by the improper inhaler technique reaches the gastrointestinal tract rather than the lungs. Besides, repeated high-dose ICS inhalation for many years is likely to have cumulative effects [7-9]. Pulmonary comorbidities are present in most of the patients presenting to haematology clinics, and also ICS use is common. Because complete blood count is a fast and straightforward laboratory test that is routinely used in the follow-up of many diseases, it can be stated that hematologic interpretation on hemogram can be critical in the course of COPD.

Additionally, there are studies on the prognostic role of hemogram parameters derived from complete blood count in various diseases [10]. While it is well known that systemic steroids may cause changes in hemogram parameters using adrenal axis, inflammation cascade and direct mediators, it is also crucial whether the use of ICS plays a role in the investigation of possible hemogram changes. Such a relationship can guide both the predictability of systemic effects of ICS and the necessity to question the use of ICS in haematological evaluations. However, the number of studies on the effects of ICSs on hemogram parameters is very limited. In this study, we aimed to find out whether ICSs have effects on hemogram and whether these possible effects are related to inhaler technique or steroid form.

Subjects and Methods

We obtained approval from the ethics committee to use patients' medical records for our study. The records of COPD patients followed up at our Chest Diseases polyclinic were reviewed retrospectively. The screening was continued until we reached 100 COPD patients using ICSs and 100 COPD patients who did not use ICSs and meet the inclusion criteria. Newly diagnosed patients were not included in terms of reflecting the long-term effects of ICSs. The criteria for inclusion in the study were listed as follows: follow up with a diagnosis of COPD for at least 2 years, having been using the same form of ICS for at least 2 years, complete treatment compliance, no need for long-term oxygen therapy and to have complete blood count taken in the last 3 months in stable period. The mean of all examinations was taken in patients who had more than one complete blood count in the previous three months. Reasons for exclusion were history of an infection for the last 3 months, presence of endocrine disorders including diabetes mellitus, oxygen dependence, having a diagnosis of chronic renal failure, history of immunosuppressive and / or anti-inflammatory therapy except for ICSs, having used systemic steroids in the last 6 months, active malignancy and hematological diseases, using anticoagulants, and having had significant bleeding or surgery in the last 1 year.

Complete blood count values including hemoglobin (HGB), red blood cell (RBC), hematocrit (HCT), red cell distribution width-coefficient of variation (RDW-CV), mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin (MCH), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC), white blood cell (WBC), neutrophil percentage (Neutrophil%), lymphocyte percentage (Lymphocyte%), monocyte percentage (Monocyte%), eosinophil percentage (Eosinophil%), basophil percentage (Basophil%), absolute neutrophil count ($\#$ Neutrophil), absolute lymphocyte count ($\#$ Lymphocyte), absolute monocyte count ($\#$ Monocyte), absolute eosinophil count ($\#$ Eosinophil), absolute basophil count ($\#$ Basophil) were recorded. Demographic data, GOLD groups, history of pneumonia in the last year, the content of bronchodilator treatments and valid inhaler techniques were recorded.

Relationships of investigated parameters were evaluated statistically. The mean and \pm standard deviation (SD) for all variables were calculated. The obtained data were analyzed by SPSS for Mac 20.0 package program (SPSS Inc, Chicago, IL, USA). Frequency and percentage for discrete data, mean \pm SD for continuous variables were used in descriptive statistics. The normality of the continuous variables was analyzed with the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test. An assessment of correlations, Pearson test, was used for data with parametric distribution and Spearman for data with non-parametric distribution. Mean values with parametric distribution between groups were analyzed by Student's T-test and ANOVA. Mean values with non-parametric distributions were compared by Mann-Whitney U and Kruskal-Wallis H tests. P-value less than 0.05 was considered as statistically significant.

Results

- Demographic data of subjects Of the 100 patients who had not used ICS (non-users), 56 were male, and 44 were female. Of 100 patients had been using ICS (users), 64 were male, and 36 were female. The male / female ratios were not significantly different between the groups. The mean age of the ICS users was 73.7 ± 10.2 years, whereas the mean age

Table 1 Comparison of clinical characteristics of patients using ICSs and patients using a bronchodilator without ICS. (ICS: inhaled corticosteroid, BMI: body-mass index, COPD: chronic obstructive pulmonary disease).

		ICS non-users	ICS users	<i>p</i>
Age (year)		62,6 ± 7,3	73,7 ± 10,2	0,045
Gender (male/female)		1,27 (56/44)	1,77 (64/36)	NS
COPD diagnosis time (years)		5,2 ± 2,6	12,4 ± 4,8	<0,001
GOLD	Proportion of GOLD-A	53 (%)	17 (%)	0,001
	Proportion of GOLD-B	26 (%)	20 (%)	NS
	Proportion of GOLD-C	14 (%)	38 (%)	0,012
	Proportion of GOLD-D	7 (%)	25 (%)	0,001
ICS use time (years)		-	8,5 ± 2,3	-
ICS form	Budesonide	-	38 (%)	-
	Fluticasone propionate	-	27 (%)	-
	Fluticasone furoate	-	11 (%)	-
	Beclomethasone	-	24 (%)	-
Inhaler technique	Dry powder inhaler (DPI)	-	53 (%)	-
	Metered Dose Inhaler (MDI)	-	32 (%)	-
	Nebulizer	-	15 (%)	-
Pneumonia in the last 1 year		3 (%)	9 (%)	0,038

of the non-users was 62.6±7.3 years and the mean age of the ICS users was significantly higher (p=0.045). When the history of COPD was examined, the history of COPD was substantially longer in ICS users than non-users (12.4±4.8 and 5.2±2.6 years respectively; p<0.001). The distribution according to the GOLD classification also showed heterogeneity between the groups. While 53% of ICS non-users were GOLD-A; 38% of the patients were GOLD-C, and 25% were GOLD-D in ICS users (p=0.001, p=0.012, p=0.001 respectively). When the ICS preparations in the treatment were examined, it was observed that the most commonly used ICS form was Budesonide with a frequency of 38%, and the most preferred inhaler technique was dry powder inhalers with a frequency of 53%. When the history of pneumonia in the last year was questioned, pneumonia was diagnosed in 6% of ICS non-users and 14% of ICS users, and the difference between the groups was significant (p=0.038) (Table 1).

- Comparison of hemogram parameters between ICS non-users and users Complete blood count parameters of ICS non-users and users were examined. Significant increase was detected in the mean MCHC, Eosinophil%, #Eosinophil values among patients who had not used ICSs; and the mean RDW-CV, MCV, WBC, Neutrophil% and #Neutrophil values among patients who had been using ICSs (p=0.045, p=0.001, p=0.005, p=0.048, p=0.05, p=0.04, p=0.037, p=0.044 respectively). The greatest difference was found in eosinophil levels. Anaemia was observed in 16 (%) of ICS non-users and 31 (%) of ICS users. This difference was statistically significant too (p=0.05) (Table 2).
- Comparison of findings according to the active ingredient of ICS When the groups were examined according to ICS ac-

tive substances, 38 (%) patients used budesonide, 27(%) patients used fluticasone propionate, 11 (%) patients used fluticasone furoate and 24 (%) patients used beclomethasone. Mean age was significantly different between all groups (p=0.033). Patients using budesonide had the highest mean age (79.1±8.4 years), while those using fluticasone furoate had the lowest mean age (64.7±4.5 years). Comparing the history of pneumonia in the last year, it was observed that the fluticasone propionate group had the highest rate of pneumonia (11.1%, 3/27 patients) (p=0.05) (Table 3).

Hemogram parameters were also compared between ICS groups. There was no significant difference between the groups in the erythrocyte series (Table 3). MPV was significantly higher in the fluticasone furoate group than the other groups (p=0.046). WBC, Neutrophil%, #Neutrophil were significantly lower in budesonide group compared to other groups (p=0.012, p=0.05, p=0.048 respectively). The mean Monocyte% and #Monocyte were significantly lower in the beclomethasone group compared to the other groups (p=0.043 and p=0.05, respectively). Fluticasone furoate group had the highest mean WBC value (9.7±2.8x10³cell/μL). Beclomethasone group had the highest mean Neutrophil% level (70.6%) (Table 3).

- Comparison of findings according to the inhaler technique used ICS users were also classified according to inhaler techniques. 62 (%) patients had been using dry powder inhaler (DPI), 28 (%) had been using a metered-dose inhaler (MDI), and 10 (%) had been using nebulizer. While 35 (%) of the DPI users had been using capsule-based DPIs, 27 (%) had been using blister-based DPIs. In general, the most commonly used form was capsule-based DPIs. The mean age was significantly different between all groups

Table 2 Comparison of hemogram parameters between inhaled corticosteroid non-users and users. (ICS: inhaled corticosteroid, HGB: hemoglobin, RBC: red blood cell, HCT: hematocrit, RDW-CV: red cell distribution width-coefficient of variation, MCV: mean corpuscular volume, MCH: mean corpuscular hemoglobin, MCHC: mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration, WBC: white blood cell, Neut%: neutrophil percentage, Lymp%: lymphocyte percentage, Mono%: monocyte percentage, Eos%: eosinophil percentage, Baso%: basophil percentage, #neut: absolute neutrophil count, #lymp: absolute lymphocyte count, #mono: absolute monocyte count, #eos: absolute eosinophil count, #baso: absolute basophil count)

	ICS non-users	ICS users	<i>p</i>
HGB (g/L)	12,7 ± 2,4	13,1 ± 3,1	NS
RBC (x10 ³ cell/μL)	3,9 ± 2,2	4,2 ± 2,5	NS
HCT (%)	42,8 ± 4,3	44,6 ± 3,9	NS
RDW-CV (%)	12,5 ± 2,1	14,6 ± 3,2	0,048
MCV (fL)	87,4 ± 4,2	92,8 ± 5,7	0,05
MCH (pg)	29,1 ± 2,5	30,2 ± 3,2	NS
MCHC (g/L)	33,7 ± 3,3	31,4 ± 3,6	0,045
MPV (fL)	10,8 ± 1,7	9,4 ± 1,2	NS
Platelet (x10 ³ cell/L)	270 ± 55	315 ± 62	NS
WBC (x10 ³ cell/μL)	6,7 ± 2,3	8,9 ± 2,5	0,04
Neut %	46,3	61,8	0,037
Lymp %	38,8	31,5	NS
Mono %	7,5	4,5	NS
Eos %	5,9	1,1	0,001
Baso %	1,5	1,1	NS
#neut (x10 ³ cell)	3,1 ± 1,4	5,5 ± 2,3	0,044
#lymp (x10 ³ cell)	2,6 ± 0,8	2,8 ± 0,9	NS
#mono (x10 ³ cell)	0,5 ± 0,2	0,4 ± 0,1	NS
#eos (x10 ³ cell)	0,4 ± 0,2	0,1 ± 0,04	0,005
#baso (x10 ³ cell)	0,1 ± 0,05	0,1 ± 0,05	NS

Table 3 (Abbreviations: HGB: hemoglobin, RBC: red blood cell, HCT: hematocrit, RDW-CV: red cell distribution width-coefficient of variation, MCV: mean corpuscular volume, MCH: mean corpuscular hemoglobin, MCHC: mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration, WBC: white blood cell, Neut%: neutrophil percentage, Lymp%: lymphocyte percentage, Mono%: monocyte percentage, Eos%: eosinophil percentage, Baso%: basophil percentage, #neut: absolute neutrophil count, #lymp: absolute lymphocyte count, #mono: absolute monocyte count, #eos: absolute eosinophil count, #baso: absolute basophil count). (Notes: a, significant differences among all groups; b, significantly different compared to budesonide; (*), the statistical analysis is pointless because the acceptability of the automated whole blood counting device is low for small amounts of cells).

	Budesonide	Fluticasone propionate	Fluticasone furoate	Beclomethasone	P
N (%)	38 (%)	27 (%)	11 (%)	24 (%)	-
Age (mean ± SD)	79,1 ± 8,4	74,5 ± 8,1	64,7 ± 4,5	68,4 ± 8,2	0,033^a
Pneumonia in the last 1 year	3 (7,9 %)	3 (11,1 %) ^b	1 (9,1 %)	2 (8,3 %)	0,05
HGB (g/L)	13,2 ± 3,1	13,2 ± 2,8	13,1 ± 2,9	12,8 ± 3,2	NS
RBC (x10³ cell/μL)	4,3 ± 2,4	4,1 ± 2,3	4,2 ± 2,6	4,1 ± 2,5	NS
HCT (%)	45,1 ± 3,8	44,2 ± 3,2	43,8 ± 3,5	44,6 ± 3,7	NS
RDW-CV (%)	14,8 ± 2,8	14,2 ± 3,1	14,5 ± 2,7	14,8 ± 2,5	NS
MCV (fL)	91,6 ± 4,7	93,1 ± 5,1	92,8 ± 5,2	94,4 ± 5,2	NS
MCH (pg)	29,7 ± 2,6	30,9 ± 3,1	31,1 ± 2,9	29,8 ± 3,2	NS
MCHC (g/L)	30,8 ± 3,1	31,7 ± 3,4	32,6 ± 3,5	31,5 ± 2,9	NS
MPV	8,9 ± 1,1	9,3 ± 1,3	10,6 ± 1,3 ^a	9,7 ± 1,2	0,046
Platelet (x10³ cell/μL)	295 ± 58	332 ± 64	324 ± 62	323 ± 65	NS
WBC (x10³ cell/μL)	7,3 ± 2,1 ^a	9,4 ± 2,6	9,7 ± 2,8	9,2 ± 2,2	0,012
Neut %	59,8 ^a	63,5	64,1	70,6	0,05
Lymp %	32,8	30,5	29,2	36,9	NS
Mono %	4,9	5,1	5,1	2,2 ^a	0,043
Eos %	1,4	1,1	0,6	1,1	NS
Baso %	1,1	0,9	1,0	1,1	NS
#neut (x10³cell)	4,4 ± 2,1 ^a	5,9 ± 2,4	6,2 ± 2,2	6,5 ± 2,5	0,048
#lymp (x10³cell)	2,4 ± 0,9	2,8 ± 1,0	2,8 ± 0,8	3,4 ± 0,9	NS
#mono (x10³cell)	0,4 ± 0,1	0,5 ± 0,1	0,5 ± 0,1	0,2 ± 0,05 ^a	0,05
#eos (x10³cell)	0,1 ± 0,05	0,1 ± 0,03	0,1 ± 0,04	0,1 ± 0,03	NS (*)
#baso (x10³cell)	0,1 ± 0,04	0,1 ± 0,04	0,1 ± 0,05	0,1 ± 0,04	NS (*)

Table 4 (ICS: inhaled corticosteroid, HGB: hemoglobin, RBC: red blood cell, HCT: hematocrit, RDW-CV: red cell distribution width-coefficient of variation, MCV: mean corpuscular volume, MCH: mean corpuscular hemoglobin, MCHC: mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration, WBC: white blood cell, Neut%: neutrophil percentage, Lymp%: lymphocyte percentage, Mono%: monocyte percentage, Eos%: eosinophil percentage, Baso%: basophil percentage, #neut: absolute neutrophil count, #lymp: absolute lymphocyte count, #mono: absolute monocyte count, #eos: absolute eosinophil count, #baso: absolute basophil count) (Notes: a, significant differences among all groups; (*), the statistical analysis is pointless because the acceptability of the automated whole blood counting device is low for small amounts of cells).

	Dry powder inhaler (DPI)		Metered Dose Inhaler (MDI)	Nebulizer	P
	Capsule	Blister			
n, %	35 (%)	27 (%)	28 (%)	10 (%)	-
Age (mean ± SD)	76,6 ± 8,9	72,1 ± 9,1	67,6 ± 6,3	83,9 ± 5,1	0,021^a
Pneumonia in the last 1 year	2 (5,7%)	3 (1,1%)	1 (3,6%)	3 (30%) ^a	0,05
HGB (g/L)	13,1 ± 2,7	13,4 ± 3,1	13,2 ± 3,0	13,0 ± 2,9	NS
RBC (x10³ cell/μL)	4,0 ± 2,3	4,2 ± 2,4	4,3 ± 2,5	4,6 ± 2,4	NS
HCT (%)	43,7 ± 3,8	44,3 ± 3,7	44,7 ± 3,6	48,3 ± 3,5	NS
RDW-CV (%)	14,3 ± 3,0	14,7 ± 2,7	14,6 ± 2,5	15,4 ± 2,7	NS
MCV (fL)	92,5 ± 4,8	92,9 ± 4,9	93,1 ± 5,1	92,7 ± 5,0	NS
MCH (pg)	29,6 ± 3,1	30,1 ± 2,8	30,3 ± 2,9	32,3 ± 3,2	NS
MCHC (g/L)	30,7 ± 3,1	31,5 ± 2,8	31,7 ± 2,9	32,7 ± 3,2	NS
MPV	9,2 ± 1,1	9,4 ± 1,2	9,3 ± 1,2	10,4 ± 1,3 ^a	0,034
Platelet (x10³ cell/L)	305 ± 61	310 ± 63	324 ± 59	338 ± 62	NS
WBC (x10³ cell/μL)	8,5 ± 1,8	9,4 ± 2,3 ^a	8,9 ± 2,1	8,9 ± 2,2	0,044
Neut %	65,9	62,8	59,6	59,5	NS
Lymp %	28,2	29,8	31,5	32,6	NS
Mono %	4,7	5,3	5,6	5,6	NS
Eos %	1,1	0,5	2,2	1,1	NS (*)
Baso %	1,1	1,1	1,1	1,1	NS (*)
#neut (x10³cell)	5,6 ± 2,1	5,9 ± 2,4	5,3 ± 2,3	5,3 ± 1,7	NS
#lymp (x10³cell)	2,4 ± 0,9	2,8 ± 0,9	2,8 ± 1,0	2,9 ± 0,6	NS
#mono (x10³cell)	0,4 ± 0,1	0,5 ± 0,1	0,5 ± 0,05	0,5 ± 0,05	NS
#eos (x10³cell)	0,1 ± 0,05	0,05 ± 0,01	0,2 ± 0,01	0,1 ± 0,01	NS (*)
#baso (x10³cell)	0,1 ± 0,01	0,1 ± 0,01	0,1 ± 0,01	0,1 ± 0,01	NS (*)

($p=0.021$). MDI had the lowest mean age (67.6 ± 6.3 years), while nebulizer users had the highest mean age (83.9 ± 5.1 years). When the pneumonia histories in the last year were compared, it was observed that the nebulizer users had the highest frequency (30%) ($p=0.05$). On the other hand, it was thought that this situation may have arisen due to the low number of nebulizer users and the higher mean age of the nebulizer group (Table 4). Hemogram parameters were also compared among the inhaler techniques used. The erythrocyte series did not show any significant difference between the groups. MPV was significantly higher in nebulizer users compared to other groups ($p=0.034$). The mean WBC was considerably higher in blister-based DPI users than in the other groups ($9.4\pm 2.3\times 10^3\text{cell}/\mu\text{L}$) ($p=0.044$). Other hemogram parameters did not show significant difference between the groups (Table 4).

- Evaluation of patients diagnosed with pneumonia in the last year Of the 12 patients who were diagnosed with pneumonia in the last year, 3 (25%) were ICS non-users, and 9 (75%) were ICS users. The frequency of pneumonia was increased by threefold/year in ICS users. Among the ICS users, the mean WBC and $\#$ Neutrophil values of these nine patients were significantly higher than those without pneumonia history ($10.8\pm 2.5\times 10^3\text{cell}/\mu\text{L}$ and $6.3\pm 2.3\times 10^3\text{cell}$; $p=0.042$ and $p=0.05$, respectively). However, there was no similar significant difference in patients with a history of pneumonia and had not been using ICSs. The mean age of these 9 ICS users and 3 ICS non-users were also significantly higher than the others ($78.9\pm 5.7\times 10^3\text{cell}/\mu\text{L}$ and $74.6\pm 6.1\times 10^3\text{cell}$; $p=0.05$ and $p=0.05$, respectively). The duration of ICS use was also significantly higher in those who had been diagnosed with pneumonia in the last year (12.5 ± 3.4 years).

Discussion

Cortisone, which was firstly extracted from the adrenal cortex in 1936, has been used in the treatment of asthma since 1950. However, several side effects of systemic steroid treatment including hypertension, osteoporosis, diabetes, obesity, facial mooning, acne, skin thinning and bruising had been identified within a few years. Consequently, researchers into safer administration of steroids led to the development of inhaled corticosteroids (ICSs) in the early 1970s [1,11-13]. ICSs, which were previously used only in the treatment of asthma, have started to be included in the treatment of COPD as the role of inflammation in the pathogenesis of COPD becomes clear in the following years. In the 1990s, short-term studies of ICS monotherapy in COPD found that anti-inflammatory therapy reduced bronchial inflammation. In a 6-month study, fewer exacerbations occurred in patients treated with ICSs compared with placebo. These data, in conjunction with the effectiveness of ICSs in the treatment of asthma, encouraged routine use of ICSs in the treatment of COPD [14,15]. Since then, the role of ICS, which has been an indispensable part of COPD treatment for a long time, has been limited to selected cases according to the GOLD guidelines published in recent years[16].

Although ICSs have been developed to minimize the serious adverse effects of steroids and have been found to be successful in this direction, some systemic effects of ICSs that reach the systemic circulation from topical use are also reported. Significant side effects of ICSs are oral candidiasis, pneumonia, ocular effects, skin effects, endocrinological effects and bone

effects [2,4,5,17,18]. One of the main points in combating the side effects of ICS is a good understanding of how ICSs reaches the systemic circulation. Contrary to what is believed, the absorption of the drug from the airways plays a more significant role rather than ingestion into the gastrointestinal tract to reach systemic circulation. It has been demonstrated that 60-90% of the ICS dose from an MDI or DPI lands in the oropharynx and is swallowed and absorbed from the gastrointestinal tract. Although this portion of ICS is then primarily metabolized by the liver ("first-pass metabolism"), a small amount is absorbed into the systemic circulation.

On the other hand, 10-40% of the ICS dose is delivered to the respiratory tract, and this fraction is absorbed from the lung tissue periphery directly into the systemic circulation. Thence, although less amount of the dose is delivered to the respiratory tract, airways are responsible for most of the amount that contributes to systemic circulation. Considering that topical administration of ICS from lung tissue is the main responsible for systemic effects, it is quite reasonable that variables such as form, dosage, active substance, molecular size, application technique of the steroid may play a determining role on these side effects [7-9].

It is a fact that many patients presenting to haematology outpatient clinics have COPD comorbidity. Some of these patients are referred for examination of polycythemia, anaemia, leukocytosis, thrombocytosis, etc. On the other hand, changes in the adrenal axis are closely related to the results of bone marrow and therefore complete blood count. When all these are considered, the effects of COPD and ICSs on the hemogram parameters should be well known. There are some studies on this subject in the literature [19-21]. One of the pioneering studies in this field is Cameron et al.'s study in which they investigated the effects of oral prednisone and inhaled beclomethasone dipropionate on circulating leukocytes in comparison [22]. This study demonstrated a similar increase in neutrophils as a percentage of the total white count and a significant decrease in the total lymphocyte number with both oral and inhaler groups. Another one of the most remarkable studies related to this hypothesis is Pesternak et al.'s study [23]. Pesternak et al. performed a randomized comparative study on 60 healthy adults. They measured the effects of a single-dose inhalation of budesonide and fluticasone on WBC and the differential leukocyte count, especially the absolute neutrophil count. They observed that both budesonide and fluticasone increased the mean WBC and absolute neutrophil count levels.

Additionally, they observed a significant decrease in the expression of the adhesion neutrophil ligands Mac-1 (CD11b) and L-selectin (CD62L). They concluded that the enhancing effects of ICSs on WBC and neutrophil numbers are the result of a decrease in the number of adhesion molecules and an increase in the number of neutrophils in circulation [23]. Our results also demonstrated significant increase in WBC, Neutrophil%, $\#$ Neutrophil in ICS users. This increase was most notable in those using fluticasone as the active ingredient of ICS and those using blister-based DPI as inhaler technique. It is remarkable that most of previous similar studies were performed in healthy volunteers and were short-term studies based on single breath inhalation measurements. In our study, longer-term real-life data obtained from COPD patients are shared. We think that this study design may better reflect the long term effects of ICSs.

Nevertheless, studies are indicating that there is no significant relationship between ICS and neutrophil levels and that

ICS only affects eosinophil levels [24,25]. Derom et al. stated that total WBC count, as well as neutrophils, basophils, lymphocytes, and monocytes, were not affected by ICS [24]. However, both fluticasone and budesonide resulted in a dose-dependent decrease in eosinophils with no significant difference between groups. Although our results are mainly consistent with these studies in terms of changes in eosinophil amounts; alterations on other hemogram parameters including WBC, Neutrophil% and \downarrow Neutrophil levels with the use of ICS were quite significant, unlike these studies.

Different mechanisms regarding the effects of ICS on hemogram parameters have been held responsible. While there are publications indicating that such effects occur on the adrenal axis and therefore enhanced release of neutrophils from bone marrow, there are also studies showing that the effects on WBC and neutrophils are results of delayed apoptosis, decreased adhesion molecules, reduced migration of neutrophils into tissues, and a shift of neutrophils from the marginating to the circulating pool, and the effects on eosinophils are in relationship with the anti-inflammatory effects of ICSs on cytokines [3,17,22,23,26,27]. We think that more than one of these mechanisms may play a role together.

To sum up the results in general; the increase in WBC and neutrophil levels, and the decrease in eosinophil levels in ICS users, the more frequent monitoring of anemia and pneumonia in ICS users, and the more pronounced WBC and neutrophil increases in the patients diagnosed with pneumonia in the last year are should be mentioned as the most remarkable findings of this study. Besides, the correlations between hemogram alterations and the frequency of pneumonia, which can be accepted as clinical evidence of systemic effect of ICSs, can be interpreted as complete blood count results may also be used as a useful marker for predicting systemic effects of ICSs.

In conclusion, the results of the study indicate that changes in hemogram parameters may be associated with ICS use and that these changes may help predict systemic side effects of ICSs. We think that this study differs from previous studies due to both its content about the analysis of real-life data and its design. While most of the previous studies examined the short-term results of single-breath inhalation, we aimed to demonstrate the cumulative effect of ICSs in the long term. Also, we could not meet any similar study comparing both active agents of ICSs and the inhalation techniques in the current literature. We believe that this study brought a different perspective in this respect, and further molecular studies will clarify this issue.

Conflict of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest to declare by any of the authors of this study.

Funding

None

References

1. Geddes DM. Inhaled corticosteroids: benefits and risks. *Thorax*. 1992;47(6):404-407. doi: 10.1136/thx.47.6.404
2. Lipworth BJ. Systemic adverse effects of inhaled corticosteroid therapy: A systematic review and meta-analysis. *Arch Intern Med*. 1999;159(9):941-955. doi: 10.1001/archinte.159.9.941
3. Barnes PJ, Pedersen S, Busse WW. Efficacy and safety of inhaled corticosteroids. New developments. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*. 1998;157(3pt2): S1-S53. doi: 10.1164/ajrccm.157.3.157315
4. Nieto A, Mazon A, Pamies R, et al. Adverse effects of inhaled corticosteroids in funded and nonfunded studies. *Arch Intern Med*. 2007;167(19):2047-2053. doi: 10.1001/archinte.167.19.2047
5. Roland NJ, Bhalla RK, Earis J. The local side effects of inhaled corticosteroids: current understanding and review of the literature. *Chest*. 2004;126(1):213-219. doi: 10.1378/chest.126.1.213
6. Hanania NA, Chapman KR, Kesten S. Adverse effects of inhaled corticosteroids. *Am J Med*. 1995;98(2):196-208. doi: 10.1016/S0002-9343(99)80404-5
7. Johnson M. Pharmacodynamics and pharmacokinetics of inhaled glucocorticoids. *J Allergy Clin Immunol*. 1996;97(1pt2):169-176. doi: 10.1016/s0091-6749(96)80217-x
8. Brutsche MH, Brutsche IC, Munawar M, et al. Comparison of pharmacokinetics and systemic effects of inhaled fluticasone propionate in patients with asthma and healthy volunteers: a randomised crossover study. *Lancet*. 2000;356(9229):556-561. doi: 10.1016/S0140-6736(00)02581-2
9. Derendorf H, Nave R, Drollmann A, Cerasoli F, Wurst W. Relevance of pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of inhaled corticosteroids to asthma. *Eur Respir J*. 2006;28(5):1042-1050. doi: 10.1183/09031936.00074905
10. Ocal R, Arslan Y. Prognostic value of hematological parameters in geriatric patients hospitalized in intensive care units. *Turkish Journal of Geriatrics*. 2019;22 (1):2-8. doi: 10.31086/tjgeri.2019150566
11. Tashkin DP, Strange. Inhaled corticosteroids for chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: what is their role in therapy? *International Journal of COPD*. 2018;13(1):2587-2601. doi: 10.2147/COPD.S172240
12. Crompton G. A brief history of inhaled asthma therapy over the last fifty years. *Primary Care Respiratory Journal*. 2006;15(6):326-331. doi: 10.1016/j.pcrj.2006.09.002
13. Confalonieri M, Mainardi E, Della Porta R, et al. Inhaled corticosteroids reduce neutrophilic bronchial inflammation in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *Thorax*. 1998;53(7):583-585. doi: 10.1136/thx.53.7.583
14. Paggiaro PL, Dahle R, Bakran I, Frith L, Hollingworth K, Efthimiou J. Multicentre randomised placebo-controlled trial of inhaled fluticasone propionate in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease. *International COPD Study Group*. *Lancet*. 1998;351(9105):773-780. doi: 10.1016/s0140-6736(97)03471-5
15. Pauwels RA, Löfdahl C-G, Laitinen LA, et al. Long-term treatment with inhaled budesonide in persons with mild chronic obstructive pulmonary disease who continue smoking. *N Engl J Med*. 1999;340(25):1948-1953. doi: 10.1056/NEJM199906243402503

16. Singh D, Agusti A, Anzueto A, et al. Global Strategy for the Diagnosis, Management, and Prevention of Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease: the GOLD science committee report 2019. *Eur Respir J.* 2019;53(5):pii:1900164. doi: 10.1183/13993003.00164-2019
17. Watkins L, Soriano JB, Mortimer K. Getting risks right on inhaled corticosteroids and adrenal insufficiency. *Eur Respir J.* 2013;42(1):9-11. doi: 10.1183/09031936.00204212
18. Bafadhel M, Peterson S, de Blas MA, et al. Predictors of exacerbation risk and response to budesonide in patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease: a post-hoc analysis of three randomised trials. *Lancet Respir Med.* 2018;6(2):117-126. doi: 10.1016/S2213-2600(18)30006-7
19. Ocal R, Arslan Y, Ozgur G, Dogan D, Yildirim M, Ocal N. Do we care enough about the role of smoking in the etiology of polycythemia? *Gulhane Med J.* 2019;61(2):46-51. doi: 10.26657/gulhane.00053
20. Cheng SL. Blood eosinophils and inhaled corticosteroids in patients with COPD: systematic review and meta-analysis. *International Journal of COPD* 2018;13(1):2775-2784. doi: 10.2147/COPD.S175017
21. Evans PM, O'Connor BJ, Fuller RW, Barnes PJ, Chung KF. Effect of inhaled corticosteroids on peripheral blood eosinophil counts and density profiles in asthma. *J Allergy Clin Immunol.* 1993;91(2):643-50. doi: 10.1016/0091-6749(93)90270-p
22. Cameron RG, Black PN, Braan C, Browett PJ. A comparison of the effects of oral prednisone and inhaled beclomethasone dipropionate on circulating leukocytes. *Aust N Z J Med.* 1996;26(6):800-805. doi: 10.1111/j.1445-5994.1996.tb00628.x
23. Pasternak Y, Yarden-Bilavsky H, Kodman Y, Zoldan M, Tamary H, Ashkenazi S. Inhaled corticosteroids increase blood neutrophil count by decreasing the expression of neutrophil adhesion molecules Mac-1 and L-selectin. *Am J Emerg Med.* 2016;34(10):1977-1981. doi: 10.1016/j.ajem.2016.07.003
24. Derom E, Schoor JV, Verhaeghe W, Vincken W, Pauwels R. Systemic Effects of Inhaled Fluticasone Propionate and Budesonide in Adult Patients with Asthma. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med.* 1999;160(1):157-161. doi: 10.1164/ajrccm.160.1.9805106
25. Hastie AT, Martinez FJ, Curtis JL, et al. Association of sputum and blood eosinophil concentrations with clinical measures of COPD severity: an analysis of the SPIROMICS cohort. *Lancet Respir Med.* 2017;5(12):956-967. doi: 10.1016/S2213-2600(17)30432-0
26. Inhaled Corticosteroids and Secondary Adrenal Insufficiency Vishnu Sannarangappa, Ryan Jalleh. *The Open Respiratory Medicine Journal.* 2014;8(Suppl1:M6):93-100. doi: 10.2174/1874306401408010093
27. Agusti A, Fabbri LM, Singh D, et al. Inhaled corticosteroids in COPD: friend or foe? *Eur Respir J.* 2018;52(6):pii:1801219. doi: 10.1183/13993003.01219-2018.